

THE ISSUE OF SELLING AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS (FRUITS AND SERVICES)

Kholmuratova Guzal Muradovna

Abstract: Village. field-steppe. garden... When such words are mentioned, we involuntarily come to our thoughts of the tanti, hard-working people, and the fruits ripening in the sun. Farming is simple at first glance, but the industry requires a lot of construction. Today, it is not enough to know how to hold a hoe and plant a couple of crops. Farming has its own modern science, if you keep pace with it, the work done throughout the year will pay off.

Key words: Farming, husbandry, care, Chust, Germination, vegetable growing.

Planting a seed and taking care of it is different. When the sprout sprouts and yields, all your fatigue will be forgotten. But if the result is not as expected, there is bound to be disappointment. This is a very easy process that requires a lot of knowledge and experience. Today, a person who has come to terms with the earth and is aware of new technologies and innovative methods has a real source of income.

In the decision of December 15, 2021 "On measures to support the state operation of the fruit and vegetable industry, to strengthen clustering and relocation in the network", it is important to reform the industry and develop it.

According to the mutual integration of product production, processing, storage and sales processes, production of food products, production of food production and export processes, production of food production and export processes , agricultural farms and producers of other products - for the cultivation of fruits, grapes, vegetables, sugar crops, greens and medicinal plants, legumes and oil crops, loans for up to 50% of the harvest at an annual rate of 14% are provided. This means that it really opens the door to take more.

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Fruits do not lose their original taste throughout the year

The fruits grown in our Serkuyosh region are distinguished by their taste and richness in medicinal properties. The project "Sublimation drying of fruits and vegetables" launched by "Ironlit" LLC of Chust district allows to preserve the natural taste and aroma of fruits for a long time.

Another advantage of this technology is that the surplus agricultural products that are tried do not go to waste, on the contrary, they become a great source of income due to neat packaging and good storage. Such stored products also provide quick food for tourists, astronauts, and military personnel, as well as long-term reserves.

"We are all familiar with the taste of fruits and vegetables, we have loved eating them since childhood," says Khairullo Akhmedov, head of "IRONLIT" LLC, a resident of Yashnabad innovation technology park. - Conventional drying causes them to lose many of their nutrients. The method we propose preserves nutrients and vitamins. By adding water to the dried fruit, it restores its appearance, shape and weight as it was when it was cut from the tree. Sublimal product can be stored from 10 to 25 years.

Fruits have a complex of vitamins and antioxidants that protect our health and skin from the harmful effects of free radicals. Freezing, drying and packaging without artificial additives in their processing also ensures long-term preservation of natural nutrients, taste, flavor and color. High technologies are used for this.

Arc film installation equipment - a farmer's tool

Bold implementation of advanced ideas and initiatives is considered an important stage of development. By ensuring the implementation of the decree of the President of February 3, 2021 "On the further development of the system of knowledge and innovations in agriculture and the provision of modern services", the provision of science-based information and modern services to business entities, the wide introduction of scientific achievements and innovations in

production, the system of providing agroservices provides seamless integration. Funding for science is proving to be the best investment for the future.

Both economic growth and social welfare depend directly on innovation. Innovation in the field, increasing productivity and soil fertility is an important process. Land can be a treasure only if a modern farmer knows the verb of every inch of land.

Small greenhouses, that is, films installed in small rows in an arc shape, are useful for growing seedlings and seedlings. When these coatings are installed using special equipment, they are excellent beam-on-beam. "Kardar Production Products" LLC in Nukus district produces equipment for mounting films in an arc shape in agriculture. This tool will help to double the income of farms engaged in pulse crops and vegetable cultivation. The equipment saves manual labor and protects crops during the early, cold days of spring.

Currently, it is possible to bring the activity of farms to the level of industrial production by implementing the mechanism of planting seedlings under a small arc-shaped film in agriculture. The technology has a number of advantages over the traditional planting method. In particular, depending on the climatic conditions, farms can get a large profit from the harvest due to planting crops in early spring. In addition, it takes time and money to weed conventionally planted seedlings, as harmful plants grow around them. And under the film, there is no bioflora for the growth of foreign plants, therefore, a positive environment is created for the planted seedling. Also, in this way, moisture is preserved for a long time and does not cause the problem of water shortage.

Agricultural technologies based on science are being introduced in viticulture Today, agriculture is becoming a branch of industry that requires science. Relying on the modern achievements of geneticists, microbiologists and other scientists, it is possible to grow many varieties of local fruits and vegetables and develop advanced technologies. The development of viticulture, which is considered one of

the important branches of the agro-industrial complex, on the basis of scientific research and research is the demand of the times. In our republic, 40 districts are specialized in viticulture, with a total of 50,000 hectares of vineyards. 45% of them are grapevines, 35% are edible and only 20% are industrial grapevines.

Taking into account the soil, climate and water conditions of these districts, science-based agro-technologies are being widely introduced in the creation of new varieties of industrial grapes in order to grow exportable grape varieties.

The Ministry of Innovative Development has allocated necessary funds for a number of projects on the development of viticulture. As a result of the implementation of these projects, high-clearance gantry type tractors, aggregated with a set of viticulture machines, resource-saving equipment for processing gardens and vineyards were developed.

In order to widely use scientific technologies in the field, practical work is being carried out on the in-depth analysis of grape genomes, the identification of candidate genes and markers, the cultivation of new seedless varieties, the creation of exportable fodder and promising technical varieties, the in-vitro propagation of vines in vineyards, and the propagation of mother seedlings.

An agreement on the development of viticulture was signed between the Ministry of Innovative Development and the National Research Center of the Kurchatov Institute of the Russian Federation, which provides for the improvement of grape varieties for winemaking.

Today, our country is becoming an agriculturally developed country. It is evident that the farming culture and rich experience founded by our ancestors are being effectively used, science and production are integrated in the field, and the principles of free market relations are being introduced.

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